

Fig. 2. The bursa copulatrix and spermatophore of *S. incertulas*: (A) bursa copulatrix of virgin female, (B) bursa copulatrix of mated female, (C) bursa copulatrix of mated female that had laid eggs, (D) spermatophore after removal from bursa copulatrix.

References

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A genomic library of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* in the broad host range mobilizing *Escherichia coli* strain S17-1

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We used molecular genetic techniques to identify virulence functions of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (*Xoo*). These studies are being conducted on an *Xoo* strain (BXO1) that belongs to a pathotype (Ib) that is widely distributed in India. Functional complementation of virulence-deficient *Xoo* mutants by mobilizing a genomic library of BXO1 (Rajagopal et al 1996) requires the transfer of many individual clones into each mutant strain.

Gene transfer into the BXO1 strain by triparental matings, wherein a plasmid (pRK600) in the helper *E. coli* strain provides the mobilization functions required in *trans*, was extremely low (1 cfu 10^9 recipient cells) and often resulted in a lack of transconjugants. This suggested the presence of a restriction barrier in the BXO1 strain. Two restriction-modification (r-m) systems have been reported from Philippine strains of *Xoo*-*XorI* and *XorII* (Choi and Leach 1994). The isochizomers

of these enzymes are *PstI* and *PvuI*, respectively. Genomic DNA isolated from the BXO1 strain was digested to completion by these enzymes, indicating the absence of *XorI* and *XorII* r-m systems in BXO1.

We assumed that if there indeed existed an r-m system in BXO1, then gene transfer frequencies would be far higher when plasmid DNA was introduced from BXO1 into BXO1 compared with transfer frequencies between *E. coli* and BXO1. Therefore, two random clones from the BXO1 genomic library (pLR17 and pLR18), each with an approximate insert size of 35

kb, were individually mobilized into *Xoo*. Plasmid DNA was isolated separately from the *E. coli* DH5a and *Xoo* strains harboring the pLR17 and pLR18 plasmids. Approximately equal amounts of plasmid DNA were electroporated into competent cells of BXO1. The frequency of electroporation was reduced by at least a thousandfold when plasmid DNA was electroporated from *E. coli* to BXO1 (Table 1). The pLR17 DNA isolated from *E. coli* was also transformed into *E. coli* DH5a competent cells to confirm that there were no deficiencies in transformation from *E. coli* to *E. coli* or

Table 1. Frequency of gene transfer into BXO1.

Donor	Frequency of transformants in BXO1 (no. of kan ^r colonies μ g ⁻¹ of plasmid DNA)
<i>E. coli</i> /pLR17	2.00×10^2
BXO1/pLR17	4.25×10^5
<i>E. coli</i> /pLR18	<1
BXO1/pLR18	3.12×10^5

other artifacts. These results suggest a rate-limiting process during transformation from *E. coli* to *Xoo*, which might be due to the existence of a previously unidentified r-m system in BXO1.

To overcome this restriction barrier, we transferred the genomic library from *E. coli* DH5a to *E. coli* S17-1. The latter strain can serve as a donor in biparental matings with *Xoo* as the *trans*-acting mobilization functions are integrated into its chromosome. Gene transfer from S17-1 in BXO1 was reasonably efficient (1 cfu 10⁻⁷ recipient cells). Therefore, approximately 1,000 clones of the BXO1 genomic library (average insert size of 30 kb) were individually mobilized by triparental matings from DH5a into S17-1. Transconjugants carrying each of the clones were individually stored at -70 °C in 96-well microtiter plates. Also, pools of

12 clones each of this library were made and can be collectively mobilized into mutants of *Xoo* to identify genes by functional complementation.

This strategy has been used successfully in our laboratory to isolate clones that complement several interesting *Xoo* mutants (Table 2). We suggest that this approach be used to isolate genomic clones that complement other mutants of *Xoo*.

References

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Table 2. Frequency of isolation of clones from *X. oryzae* pv. *oryzae* cosmic genomic library.

Nature of <i>X. oryzae</i> pv. <i>oryzae</i> genes on cloned DNA	Frequency of occurrence in <i>X. oryzae</i> pv. <i>oryzae</i> cosmic genomic library (no. of clones identified/no. of clones screened)
Genes for a Type II protein secretion system ^a	1/312
Shikimate dehydrogenase gene ^b	1/660
A gene cluster ^c encoding putative glycosyl transferase and epimerase genes	1/600

^aRequired for virulence on rice. ^bRequired for pigment production and aromatic amino acid biosynthesis. ^cRequired for extracellular polysaccharide production and virulence.

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It is not a single system for the world. It contains some generic information, but some are site- or region-specific. TropRice is intended to be a template that could be modified for different environments. As improved systems on component technologies become available, they will replace or be linked to the system. The present system is aimed at irrigated rice in a Los Baños, Philippines-type of environment.

TropRice is an ongoing project developed by IRRI scientists and specialists who have contributed to the technical content. It is intended for intermediary technology transfer agents as a response to the recognition that many farmers do not have access to information on how to grow rice. Current information technology offers new ways of packaging and presenting information. The system is being evaluated among three separate groups: nongovernment organizations, farmers, and the private and public sector.

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